

shown that picric acid and 2:4-dinitrophenol (2:4-DNP) from benzene solution are strongly sorbed by alumina (pH 3.2-5.5) but desorbed to varying extents with dioxane-water (4:1, v/v). In the present communication, we have examined the column chromatography of the solutes.

The earlier studies by other workers^{2,3,4} do not appear to have incorporated the systematic studies on the binary separation of the solutes from their synthetic mixture using Brockmann alumina.

Procedure :

Glass Column (25×1 cm) was packed dry with Brockmann alumina of pH 5.5 to a column height of 16 cm. The solutes (BDH) were recrystallised as described earlier¹, and dissolved in purified benzene (80 mg/l). 5-ml solutions were withdrawn, mixed, applied to the column, and kept as such for an hour. 2:4-DNP was eluted with 40 ml of dioxane-water (4:1) followed by picric acid with 20 ml of dioxane-acetate buffer solution of pH 5.5 (1:1, v/v). The two eluates were examined for their identity by spot test with aq KCN⁵. Eluate fractions were determined colorimetrically by developing colour with alkali, as described previously¹.

The distribution coefficients (Kd) from benzene solution were found to be as follows :

2:4-DNP...17.6, and Picric acid...32.6.

The recoveries were 99.9%.

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Oxidation of Hydrocarbons. Part II. Catalytic Oxidation of Paraffin Wax at 413°K

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THE study of oxidation of hydrocarbons has been of considerable interest for several workers¹⁻⁸. The importance of these studies is twofold. Firstly, the oxidation products have found numerous applications such as their usefulness in the manufacture of detergents, synthetic fibres, plastics and

several good quality solvents. Secondly, these studies help to understand the mechanism of these reactions.

We have undertaken a systematic study of catalytic oxidation of hydrocarbons in liquid phase. In part-1 of this series⁸ we reported kinetics of the catalytic oxidation of liquid-paraffin. The present work reports liquid phase catalytic air-oxidation of paraffin wax at 413°K. Five different cobalt salt catalysts used are cobalt naphthenate(I), cobalt bromide(II), cobalt carbonate(III), cobalt chloride (IV), and cobalt sulphate(V). Attempts have also been made to study the effects of amount of catalyst and rate of air-flow.

Experimental

Chemicals : Paraffin wax (L.R.) used had congealing point 331-333°K. Cobalt naphthenate, cobalt bromide, cobalt carbonate, cobalt chloride and cobalt sulphate (each L. R. grade) were used as such.

Method : The apparatus and the procedure used were similar as reported in part-1⁸. The temperature of oil-thermostat was kept at 413°K±0.1°. The air supply through the sample was maintained at the rate of 8.8 litres/minute (unless otherwise mentioned).

Results and Discussion

In Figure 1 plots of acid values against time have been given. Catalyst concentration in each case was

Fig. 1. Catalytic Effect of some Cobalt Salts on the Carboxylic Acid Formation using 0.400% (w/v) Catalyst at 413°K.

- Δ — Cobalt Carbonate
- ■ — Cobalt Bromide
- ○ — Cobalt Naphthenate
- □ — Cobalt Chloride
- ● — Cobalt Sulphate
- x — Without Catalyst

0.4% (w/v). Acid values of samples after seven hours of oxidation corresponding to five cobalt salts used are in the order : III>II>I>IV>V. Except for cobalt sulphate, acid values corresponding to the remaining four catalysts increase with time till 11 hours of oxidation ; after that a further increase of the carboxylic acids ceases. The rate of carboxylic acids formation in cobalt sulphate-catalysed reactions is very low, i. e., it is even less than that for non-catalysed reactions. It is believed that the phenomenon of heterogeneous catalysis is involved in hydrocarbons-oxidation. Also in the present study cobalt carbonate, though almost insoluble in paraffin wax, proved to be a most effective catalyst. Therefore, low solubility of cobalt sulphate in paraffins may not be the cause of its poor catalytic activity. At this stage it is difficult to explain for the abnormal behaviour of cobalt sulphate. However, the role of sulphur (in cobalt sulphate) as a catalytic poison in these reactions may be presumed. Scipioni and Campo⁹ observed similar catalyst poisoning effects of sulphur-containing compounds during catalytic air-oxidation of xylene.

A comparison of the values of slopes of the curve (Figure 1 ; cobalt bromide catalyst) with those of the corresponding curve for liquid paraffin⁸ indicates that the initiation curve in case of catalytic air-oxidation of paraffin wax is less as compared to liquid paraffin. It indicates that higher *n*-alkane homologues can more readily be oxidized than lower ones.

In Figure 2, the effect of catalyst concentration has been shown. Acid values after 6 hours corresponding to 0.4% (w/v) catalyst-concentration are less than that for 0.1%. Acid values increase further when the amount of catalyst is reduced to 0.025%. It once again supports⁸ the existence of critical catalyst concentration for catalytic hydrocarbons oxidation reactions. Any further increase in the amount of catalyst in excess to the critical concentration only diminish the reaction rate rather than to accelerate it. However, higher catalyst concentration slightly decreases the induction period.

Effect of air-flow rate was also studied. It was found (Fig. 3) that with a four-fold increase in the rate of air-flow (e.g., from 2.2 litres/minute to 8.8 litres/minute) the acid values of the product samples were nearly doubled. However, for both these flow rates maximum acid values were attained at 11-12 hours of oxidation. But while using air-flow rate of 0.7 litre/minute there is throughout a regular increase in carboxylic acid contents in the product.

A comparison of IR spectra of the pure paraffin wax and the product samples (catalyst cobalt bromide) revealed that two additional absorption peaks—one at 1700 cm^{-1} and the other at 1170 cm^{-1} appeared in case of product samples. The former frequency corresponds to the carbonyl stretching vibration of saturated aliphatic carboxylic acid group

Fig. 2. Effect of Amount of Catalyst on the Carboxylic Acid Formation during the Oxidation of Paraffin wax catalysed by Cobalt Bromide.

.....x.....0.00% (w/v)
▲.....0.025% (w/v)
■.....0.100% (w/v)
●.....0.400% (w/v)

Fig. 3. Effect of air flow-rate on the Carboxylic Acid Formation during Oxidation of Paraffin wax using Cobalt Naphthenate (0.400% w/v) Catalyst at 413°K.

.....▲.....0.7 Litres/Minute
●.....2.2 " "
■.....8.8 " "

and the latter is characteristic of alkylhydroperoxide group. From the peak intensities it is believed that almost no hydroperoxide (so also carboxylic

acid) are formed during first hour of oxidation. However, for samples collected at 3 hours onward the intensities of both the above mentioned peaks increase simultaneously. It suggests that attainment of almost constant acid values at 11-12 hours of oxidation is not, at least, due to exhausting of alkylhydroperoxide intermediate which is believed to take active part² in the chain-initiation and chain-propagation steps in these reactions.

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Studies in Chromones and Flavones. Part XII*

Synthesis of γ -Pyrone Derivatives from 2, 4-Diacetyl Resorcinol

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IN continuation of our previous work¹ we have now studied the synthesis of γ -pyrone derivatives from 2, 4-diacetyl resorcinol². On condensation with benzaldehyde in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide it gave the 2, 4-dicinnamoyl resorcinol (Ia) which gave a dimethyl ether and colour reactions of a chalcone derivative. It was cyclised to the isomeric 2''-phenylflavono (7, 8:6'', 5'')-pyran-4''-one (IIa) by refluxing with alcoholic hydrochloric acid. This on refluxing with palladium on charcoal in diphenyl ether gave 2''-phenylflavono (7, 8:6'', 5'') γ -pyrone (IIIa). The same product was obtained when the dicinnamoyl derivative was

refluxed with selenium dioxide in isoamyl alcohol. Its structure was proved by a stepwise synthesis from the known 7-hydroxy-8-acetyl flavone³ by condensation with benzaldehyde and cyclodehydrogenation of the 8-cinnamoyl derivative obtained with selenium dioxide. Through a similar sequence of reactions 2, 4-diacetyl resorcinol and anisaldehyde gave the corresponding 2''-(*p*-methoxyphenyl) derivative (IIIb). The Michael addition of diethyl malonate to the above dicinnamoyl derivatives gave the esters (IVa and b) which on hydrolysis and partial decarboxylation gave the dibasic acids (Va and b).

Ia, R=H
Ib, R=OCH₃

IIa, R=H
IIb, R=OCH₃

IIIa, R=H
IIIb, R=OCH₃

IVa, R=H
IVb, R=OCH₃

Va, R=H
Vb, R=OCH₃

Experimental

2, 4-Dicinnamoyl resorcinol: A mixture of 2, 4-diacetyl resorcinol² (1 g) and benzaldehyde (2 ml) in alcohol (20 ml) was kept at room temperature for 24 hrs with potassium hydroxide solution (5 g

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